

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

PAPERLESS TRADE AND DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

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Abstract

Paperless trade in Georgia and issues of its development features are discussed in the paper. The focus is on cross-border payment systems, supply chain management, trade economic transparency and security data protection. Overall, all of the above contribute to trade facilitation through a combination of digitization. All this will lead to reduction of costs and increase of transparency. And the procedures will certainly help ensure quality and compliance in the promotion and development of foreign trade.

Keywords: supply chain, one window principle, blockchain.

Introduction: An important issue for the world trading system is the bureaucratic bottlenecks and the streamlining, modernization and harmonization of trade facilitation-export and import processes.

The purpose of the research is how effectively the digitalization platform will work in the international market space. The research was conducted through a pre-structured online questionnaire, for which an online platform (Google forms) was used.

The World Trade Organization (WTO) deals with the global rules of trade between countries. Its main function is to ensure that trade flows as smoothly, predictably and freely as possible. It helps its member countries how to conduct trade relations quickly and easily, so that maximum results are achieved in the shortest possible time. How to introduce a new platform "paperless trade" and digitization. To implement and make international trade through the platform more transparent, reliable and secure.

International trade can save billions of dollars by going paperless. This increases the security of trading operations by providing electronic data. Paperless trade allows governments to reduce delays and costs at the border and increase their services to trade.

For the private sector, it can increase the efficiency of supply chains and provide new value-added services. This eliminates operational costs associated with paper processing, increasing transparency. The exchange of information between trading partners improves trade and finance processes, helps to establish new modes of cooperation between companies and integrate supply chain processes. This reduces the need for repeated data entry and reduces errors, allowing companies to develop new, value-added services such as automated tracking systems, document processing monitoring and security.

In today's environment, when different countries are developing paperless trading systems, the best way to promote interoperability is to use common international standards. When paperless trading systems are developed on the basis of common international standards, they are technologically easier to connect with each other. Paperless trade operations are carried out in a certain legal manner, while the regulatory regime takes place at the domestic level. At the national level,

governments must establish their domestic legal framework for paperless trading systems to function properly. When import legal frameworks, economies and exporting economies are not harmonized, paperless trade systems are not interoperable.

To implement paperless trade across borders, participating parties must have trading systems. The economies of the Asia and Pacific region are in a leading position in terms of free trade. Implementation of paperless trading systems requires certain experience and knowledge of relevant technologies and skills, such as: business process analysis and reengineering, data harmonization.

Challenges in Georgia

The challenge in Georgia is how to use digitalization to further the goal of industrialization. This brief examines Georgia's trade promotion strategies. A deepening of the manufacturing sector will build a more resilient economy. Our country is endowed with huge resources - in agriculture, mining and marine industry. And if properly harnessed, it can stimulate a resource-based industrialization strategy. The digitization of the economy is often seen as related to the large-scale adoption of labor-saving technologies, which requires the development of appropriate skills for the workforce to take advantage of the digital advantage. Emphasis should be placed here, especially with regard to youth employment, the use of technology to support the growth of productive sectors, sectors with high labor intensity and advancement links. The government can use such digital technologies in public administration and thus enhance the conditions of service and delivery. Georgia has the opportunity to develop industrial sectors, namely: active industrial policy on production, investments in infrastructure and capital.

Although all these are necessary, we must focus on digitization. This will help our country's manufacturers better embrace digital means. We government can use digital technology to empower society to industrialize administration.

Digitization will help enhance efficiency and productivity related to production, including customs administration, etc. This will strengthen the industrial sector.

Conclusion

At present, the implementation of measures of fair trade in our country remains very limited. This suggests that additional measures are needed in this regard. E-commerce strategies will also help boost trade. Our country should adopt an active industrial policy and use a range of industrial policy instruments to boost production. The country can use new technologies through automatic electronic exchange. Digitization enables tax and customs authorities to analyze data to identify automated risk models. These will be cases that involve a high risk of tax evasion or illegal payments. It will also help the country to more easily analyze the patterns of accounting and firms.

The WTO Trade Facilitation Agreement allows member countries to mobilize financial and technical support, such as: tariff-free trade reforms and digitization. The following tools can be considered to enhance e-commerce: e-commerce readiness assessment and strategy formulation; trade promotion; Development of

knowledge and skills. At the same time, it is important to consider the changes in the tax policy to ensure that the electronic platform does not disrupt the taxes used for the industrial policy to achieve the industrialization needed.

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